

Encapsulation and Growth of Gold Nanoparticles in Thermoresponsive Microgels**

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Nanocomposite materials that consist of a colloidal metal nanoparticle within a synthetic polymer hydrogel shell have attracted great attention owing to potential applications in several fields, such as catalysis, photonics, electronics, optics and biomedicine.^[1,2] For these applications, a precise control over the size and shape of the core particles as well as a low polydispersity are crucial issues. Among the usual polymer shells, stimuli-responsive materials^[3] are particularly interesting because of the possibilities they offer for external switching and manipulation. A common example is poly (*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM), a thermoresponsive polymer that undergoes a phase transition from a hydrophilic, water-swollen state to a hydrophobic, globular state when heated above its lower critical solution temperature (LCST), which is about 32–33 °C, in water. Addition of co-monomers has also been proposed, as a means to add responsiveness towards different stimuli such as temperature,^[4] pH,^[5] ionic strength,^[6,7] or light.^[8]

Although several reports have been recently published on the synthesis of metal nanoparticles with a wide variety of morphologies, such as spheres, rods, cubes, prisms and other polygons, with a good control over their size, morphology, and polydispersity, proper encapsulation within microgel colloids has only been reported for spheres. Different approaches have been proposed to obtain core/shell nanocomposite materials consisting of a core and a thermoresponsive pNIPAM shell.

For example, Zha et al.^[9] employed silica particles as cores, which were initially modified with 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate, providing the silica surface with terminal double bonds so as to fully encapsulate the particles by radical polymerization. Recently, Karg et al.^[10] used a similar approach for the encapsulation of silica-coated gold nanoparticles within pNIPAM shells. Metal nanoparticles have also been used as templates by Singh et al.^[11] for the growth of pNIPAM nanogels, upon priming the nanoparticle surface with a layer of amino-terminated NIPAM to facilitate the precipitation and polymerization of pNIPAM. Kim and Lee proposed two different approaches for the encapsulation of gold particles: replacement of citrate ions with oleic acid, prior to pNIPAM polymerization,^[12] and in situ synthesis and growth of nanoparticles on the surface of previously formed microgel particles.^[13]

Whereas these methods seem to work for the particular systems of choice, a more general approach is still required for the encapsulation of metal nanoparticles with a variety of sizes and shapes. The use of surfactants, and in particular cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), has proven extremely efficient for the synthesis of metal nanoparticles with a wide variety of compositions, sizes, and shapes such as spheres,^[14,15] rods,^[16] and plates.^[17,18] In addition, the adsorption properties of CTAB have been employed for the phase transfer of different inorganic nanoparticles from water into an organic solvent or vice versa. CTAB-coated small particles can also serve as substrates for the free-radical polymerization of styrene, resulting in the formation of particles with a thin polystyrene shell, as has been shown for silica.^[19] On the basis of this idea, we have developed a simple two-step procedure for the encapsulation of CTAB-stabilized metal nanoparticles with pNIPAM. The first step comprises the growth of a polystyrene (PS) shell (promoted by the CTAB bilayer), which serves to avoid aggregation and make the surface of the particles fully compatible with the precipitation polymerization of NIPAM, in the presence of a crosslinker *N,N'*-methylene bisacrylamide (BIS), during the second step.

This novel approach has been successfully applied to CTAB-stabilized spherical nanoparticles synthesized through the seeded growth method,^[15] by which the nanoparticles are stabilized by a CTAB double layer adsorbed to their surface. For PS coating, a small amount of a mixture of styrene/

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divinylbenzene in ethanol was added to the gold colloid and stirred for 15 min at 40 °C to allow the solubilization of the nearly water insoluble styrene and divinylbenzene (DVB) monomers into the CTAB admicelle adsorbed to the particles surface. These monomers were polymerized in situ by free-radical polymerization through the addition of a cationic initiator (2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionamide)dihydrochloride) (AAPH). After a suitable period of time (two hours) the sample was centrifuged to remove CTAB molecules, unreacted monomers, as well as the initiator, and redispersed in water. Figure 1A shows a negative staining (described in the

Experimental) transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of the PS-coated gold nanoparticles. The thin PS shells can be observed as a white halo around each particle. The PS/DVB shell provides the particles with sufficient stability to be dispersed in the polymerization medium used for pNIPAM microgel growth, also providing the surface of the particles with non-polymerized vinyl groups that become excellent anchor points for NIPAM polymerization. Therefore, through suitable control of the ratio of nanoparticles to emulsion droplets in the polymerization mixture it is possible to avoid or minimize the formation of free microgel spheres, since the nanoparticles act as nucleation centers for microgel formation. Figure 1B and C shows TEM images of pNIPAM-coated gold nanoparticles at different magnifications. It can be clearly seen that all particles are coated and there is no sign of aggregation. The particles are invariably well separated from each other because of the collapse of the microgel upon drying on the TEM grid.

Further characterization of the obtained nanocomposites was carried out by tapping-mode atomic force microscopy (TM-AFM), dynamic light scattering (photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS)), and UV-vis spectroscopy. Confirmation of the core/shell structure was obtained by AFM on dry core/shell microgel samples. The inset of Figure 1B shows a 3D representation of a TM-AFM image of a pNIPAM coated gold nanoparticle. As we can observe, the particle clearly stands out from its polymer surroundings. More details on the AFM imaging are given in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information. All height profiles (see Supporting Information) revealed a bump at the particle center, with diameter in good agreement with the metal core dimensions, while the soft, outer shell can be seen to have collapsed around the core during drying.

The thermoresponsive properties of the nanocomposites were characterized by PCS. Figure 2 displays the variation of

Figure 1. TEM images showing A) PS/DVB coated gold nanoparticles and B,C) Au-pNIPAM core/shell microgels at different magnifications. The inset in (B) is a tapping-mode atomic force microscopy (AFM) image of one composite particle, with a collapsed (microgel) corona around a hard (gold) core. The scale bar is 200 nm.

Figure 2. Variation of the hydrodynamic diameter of Au@pNIPAM composite particles with 67 nm gold nanoparticle cores, with temperature. Closed and open symbols denote the heating and cooling cycles, respectively.

the hydrodynamic diameter of the nanocomposites when the temperature was varied between 5 and 52 °C. A well-defined volume transition is observed around 32 °C for the Au@pNIPAM core/shell system. The reversibility of the phase transition is clearly demonstrated by the perfect match of the heating and cooling curves. Since the measured LCST is similar to that for a bare pNIPAM microgel,^[20] we can say that the presence of a metal core does not significantly affect the swelling behavior of the pNIPAM shell.

As previously shown in the literature,^[21] the volume changes of the pNIPAM shell as a function of temperature affect the surface plasmon resonance condition of the core metal nanoparticles, because of the corresponding changes in the local refractive index. UV-vis spectra were recorded of aqueous dispersions of pNIPAM-coated 67 nm gold nanoparticles, between 10 °C (completely swollen state as determined by light scattering) and 55 °C (completely collapsed microgel), as shown in Figure 3A. Two effects can be observed when temperature is increased: (a) an increase in absorbance, both at low wavelengths and at the plasmon band; and (b) a red-shift of the surface plasmon band. Both effects are likely to arise from an increase in the refractive index of the microgel during its collapse, which results in an increase of the Rayleigh scattering

Figure 3. A) UV-vis spectra of an aqueous dispersion of 67 nm gold-core@pNIPAM-shell nanoparticles at different temperatures, between 10 °C and 55 °C. B) Evolution of surface plasmon band position (open squares) and turbidity (absorbance at 400 nm, solid circles) when increasing temperature of the same sample.

because of a larger refractive index contrast with the solvent (this effect, mainly observed at lower wavelengths in the UV-vis spectra, is also observed for pure microgel particles), as well as an increase of the local refractive index around the gold nanoparticles, which leads to a red-shift (as large as 10 nm) and enhancement of the surface plasmon band, as previously reported and predicted by Mie theory.^[22,23] Both effects are summarized in Figure 3B. The variation of the absorbance at 400 nm (reflecting the increase in the turbidity of the colloid) and the surface plasmon band position of the nanoparticles (reflecting the increase of the local refractive index around the particles) were plotted against temperature. Interestingly, the evolution of both turbidity and surface plasmon position as a function of temperature qualitatively reproduce the swelling curve of the microgel measured by PCS. This is a further confirmation that the gold nanoparticles have been perfectly encapsulated by the microgel during growth.

Apart from the interesting thermoresponsive behavior of these nanocomposites, the restricted environment and the high porosity of the microgel shell offer the possibility to carry out selective chemical reactions on the encapsulated nanoparticles. A useful example of the use of these novel microreactors is shown in what follows. The idea was to grow the gold core in situ, by means of a seeded growth approach, using CTAB to avoid secondary nucleation in solution and to control the final particle size.^[15] Although the experiment was successful and core growth was observed in all cases, depending on the experimental conditions (see experimental section), the starting 67 nm gold nanoparticles can either retain their original, spherical shape or evolve into a branched, flowerlike morphology. The crucial parameter determining the final shape of the particles seems to be the concentration of CTAB used during growth, rather than the porosity of the microgel. At high CTAB concentration (0.05 M) the grown particles are roughly spherical (Fig. 4A), while at lower concentrations, such as 0.015 M, branched growth takes place from the central core, in random directions (see Fig. 4B). Both TEM and AFM characterization (Fig. 4C) confirm that the core/shell structure is maintained during growth and reveal a noticeable increase in particle size from around 67 up to around 90 nm for this particular experiment, while larger sizes can be achieved by proper choice of reactant concentrations. A remark has to be made concerning Au particle sizes measured inside the pNIPAM capsules: the diameters or heights can be influenced by the polymer presence which might consequently influence both diameters and heights. Previous studies on the interaction of surfactants (either cationic or anionic) with pNIPAM microgels have shown an increase in the deswelling ratio with increasing surfactant concentration.^[24,25] One could thus postulate that the different pore size is responsible for the morphological changes upon gold core growth. However, we have observed that the final core morphology for each CTAB concentration is almost identical, regardless of whether the reaction is carried out below or above the swelling transition temperature, which rules out a dominant porosity effect. While more experiments are required to elucidate the actual role of

Figure 4. TEM images of ca. 90 nm gold nanoparticles with A) spherical and B) flowerlike shape. C) AFM characterization of initial (top) and grown (bottom) spherical cores. D) UV-vis spectra of aqueous dispersions of the grown samples (spheres and flowers, as indicated) below (15 °C) and above (50 °C) the LCST.

CTAB, this seems to be not only to solubilize the CTA–AuCl₄ complex, but also to favor the diffusion of the complex through the pNIPAM shell owing to the concentration-dependent adsorption of CTAB inside the microgel particles.

The different morphology obtained for low and high CTAB concentrations is also reflected in their respective UV-vis spectra, as shown in Figure 4D. While the surface plasmon band of larger spheres is slightly red-shifted and broadened,^[15] for rougher, flowerlike nanoparticles the red-shift is much longer and a second band shows up at lower wavelengths, as expected for two plasmon modes, as recently reported for Au nanostars.^[26] For both types of grown particles, the temperature-driven phase transition was observed to induce a notably greater red-shift in the position of the surface plasmon band, as compared to that for smaller cores. Figure 4D shows that the spectral shift for 90 nm gold particles with spherical and flowerlike morphology amounts in both cases ca. 18 nm (see Supporting Information). Thus, controlled core growth allows us to tune the position of the plasmon band and leads to an enhanced sensitivity toward local refractive index changes.

In summary, a novel and efficient method was developed to coat CTAB-capped metal nanoparticles with pNIPAM, involving initial coating with a thin polystyrene shell and subsequent emulsion polymerization of NIPAM monomers

on the coated nanoparticles. The resulting core/shell structure was unambiguously confirmed through detailed TEM, AFM, and UV-vis spectroscopy analysis. A temperature-driven, reversible swelling–deswelling transition was identified in the core/shell system, with a transition temperature similar to that of the pure microgel system, which can be easily monitored through (reversible) surface plasmon shifts. Remarkably, the metallic cores can be grown within the microgel, leading to different morphologies as a function of CTAB concentration, which allows simple tuning of the corresponding optical response and environmental sensitivity. All these results demonstrate the accessibility of the metal cores, which is crucial for applications such as catalysis or biosensing.

Experimental

Gold nanoparticles were prepared through a seeded growth method developed by Rodríguez-Fernández et al.^[15] based on the reduction of HAuCl₄ with ascorbic acid on CTAB-stabilized Au nanoparticle seeds (~15 nm, previously prepared by citrate reduction), in the presence of 0.015 M CTAB. The nanoparticles thus synthesized had an average diameter of (67 ± 5) nm. The initial polystyrene coating was performed as follows: 150 mL of as-prepared CTAB-stabilized gold nanoparticles were centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 40 min, the supernatant was discarded, and the precipitate redispersed in 150 mL of milli-Q water. The solution was then heated to 30 °C, followed by addition of styrene (10 μL) and divinylbenzene (5 μL) under stirring. After 15 min the temperature was raised to 70 °C and the polymerization was initiated by adding 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionamide)dihydrochloride (20 μL 0.1 M in water). The polymerization was allowed to proceed for 2 h. The solution was centrifuged once at 4000 rpm (40 min), the supernatant discarded and the precipitate redispersed in 15 mL of milli-Q water. The solution was purged with nitrogen (15 min), followed by addition of *N*-isopropylacrylamide (0.1698 g) and *N,N*-methylenebisacrylamide (0.0234 g). After 15 min, the nitrogen flow was removed and the polymerization was initiated with the addition of 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionamide)dihydrochloride (150 μL 0.1 M). After 7–10 min the colorless solution became turbid and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 3 h at 70 °C. The white mixture was then allowed to cool down to room temperature under stirring. To remove small oligomers, unreacted monomers as well as gold-free microgels, the dispersion was diluted with water (15 mL) and centrifuged (30 min at 4000 rpm) and redispersed in water three times.

Further growth of pNIPAM coated gold nanoparticles was performed by seeded growth in aqueous CTAB.^[15] Spherical nanoparticles of ca. 90 nm diameter were grown in CTAB 0.05 M. Typically, 4.06 mL CTAB (0.1 M) containing 0.125 mM HAuCl₄ and

0.25 mM ascorbic acid were mixed with 0.94 mL of Au@pNIPAM ([Au]=0.64 mM, [CTAB]=0.05 M). Flowerlike nanoparticles were obtained in a similar experiment, with CTAB 0.015 M.

Characterization: UV-vis spectra were recorded using either a Cary 5000 UV-vis-NIR spectrophotometer or an Agilent 8453 UV-vis spectrophotometer. Atomic force microscopy was carried out in tapping mode with a VEECO RTE SP tip of $k=20\text{--}80\text{ N m}^{-1}$ (exact spring constant, not calculated) using a Nanoscope V controller on a multimode microscope. Transmission electron microscopy was performed by using a JEOL JEM 1010 microscope operating at an acceleration voltage of 100 kV. The negative staining of the PS-coated gold nanoparticles was performed as follows; a drop of the colloid was naturally desiccated on the TEM grid, then a drop of 2% uranyl acetate in ethanol solution (previously filtered) was dripped on the copper grid for about 60 s and the extra droplet was removed and the grid dried prior to TEM observation. Photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS) was carried out on a Zetasizer Nano S (Malvern Instruments, Malvern UK) using a detection angle of 173° . The Nano S used a 4 mW He-Ne laser operating at a wavelength of 633 nm. The intensity-averaged particle diameter and the polydispersity index values (an estimate of the distribution width) were calculated from cumulant-type analysis.

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